

ISic000655

I.Sicily inscription 000655

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

None

Last Change

2021-07-08 - Francesca Prado tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Cl]odi[ae] P(ubli) · F(iliae) □ Falconillae matri
3. Pompei · Falconis
4. Sosius (vac. undefined) Priscus
5. (vac. undefined) M [---]

Apparatus

text based on photograph

Translation (en)

To Clodia Falconilla, daughter of Publius, mother of Pompeius Falco, Sosius Priscus (built this?)...

Translation (it)

Per Clodia Falconilla, figlia di Publius, madre di Pompeius Falco, Sosius Priscus (fece?)...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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EDCS 3700328

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Bibliography

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Libertini, G 1926. Centuripe. Catania. At 42

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